
Value creation and capture in sustaining platform-based business

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Abstract: Value creation and capture aspects introduce specific requirements for sustaining a multi-sided platform-based system. The case studied is DORA, a platform-based information system for multimodal traveling optimization. Utilizing focus group methodology, we explain the requisite conditions for the emergence of an ecosystem and describe the attributes that enable the ecosystem to remain sustainably together. Analyzing positive and negative value elements for each stakeholder we find that to subscribe to the transformative effect that the platform has on their business stakeholders expect benefits in scaling up their business cost-effectively while also pursuing common goals related to platform development, fair sharing of the created value and improving the sustainability of the transport system. We also find that reorganizing into an ecosystem creates benefits especially for society and end users at the expense of traditional business models of service providers.

Keywords: Value creation; value capture; platform; ecosystem; business model; case study; mobility; multi-sided markets; sustainability; innovation

1 Introduction

Ecosystems and platform-based thinking have achieved a significant role both in business and academia (Moore 1993; Van Alstyne et al., 2016, Gawer & Cusumano, 2013). In ecosystems, several players across industries work together to collaboratively create value for multiple customer groups (Adner & Kapoor, 2010). These networks of actors are often built on a platform which works as a specific space for interaction and through which value is distributed (Li, 2009). Our study focuses on examining a platform-based information system for multimodal traveling optimization otherwise known as a mobility integrator. As a technological solution this kind of system generates value in multiple ways: financial benefits (via cost savings and revenue), societal benefits (greener, more efficient use of public transport), added use of transport services, prevention and mitigation of disruptive events etc. This generated value is considerable in total but divided unevenly across the involved stakeholders, as are also the costs of maintaining the system in operation.

Actors’ decision to connect to or adopt the ecosystem is highly linked to value appropriation (the individual share of each actor from the value created in innovation activities) i.e. value capture, thus setting directions for the management of business ecosystems (Ritala & Hurmelinna-Laukkanen, 2009). For platform-based businesses the core issue is to manage the collaboration of an ecosystem of multiple types (e.g. cities, airports, airlines, private and public transport operators) of actors in an open innovation relationship.

The success of the platform is dependent on its ability to first attract a critical mass of each key stakeholder type, and then sustain their commitment (induce lock-in). On the longer run, incentivizing innovation becomes critical as well. Thus, it is critical to balance the value generated for, and captured by, the various parties so that the total value generated by the network is maximized (Van Alstyne, et al., 2016) and each actor captures sufficient value to incentivize ongoing commitment and investment. Otherwise key stakeholders may switch to competitors, reaching critical adoption will become prohibitively costly and continued innovation of the platform and its services will be stifled - as has been the case with countless platforms that have failed to realize their potential.

Both the value creation and value capture aspects introduce specific requirements for sustaining a multi-sided platform-based system. While some successful ecosystems have managed to solve the problem (e.g. Google, PlayStation, Cisco) (Eisenmann et al., 2006), so far we have only seen case-specific solutions of private enterprises and lack sufficient management theory to provide robust, generally applicable guidelines on ecosystem design and management. Business model research still strongly focuses on how an [individual] organization creates, delivers and captures value (e.g. Baden-Fuller & Haefliger, 2013; Osterwalder et al. 2010). Previous research has emphasized the role of the hub firm operating in the center of the network in determining the success of the ecosystem and describes how hub firms create and extract value from their networks and how ecosystems are built and orchestrated (Ritala et al. 2013; Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006; Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011). The design of economic platforms and their business models is subject to the idiosyncratic requirements of operating on multi-sided markets that have two or more value providing distinct user groups (Evans & Schmalensee, 2007). In ecosystem-based business the value is created in collaboration with various partners and the captured value redistributed among the partners in a fair and equitable way, respectful of the partners’ contribution to the ecosystem and its further development (Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011).

In short, our focus is on complementing the great work of Nambisan & Sawhney (2011) and Ritala et al. (2013) in managing the ecosystems. Our questions guiding our research are: *How to get the commitment of the critical mass of service providers and customers to the platform based ecosystem? What are the required conditions for sustaining a multi-actor/multi-sided platform based ecosystem?*

We expand the understanding by focusing on sustaining ecosystem existence in industry setting where public organizations play significant role. Our research goes beyond traditional models and focuses on cooperative business models in the networked environment. We explain the requisite conditions for the emergence of an ecosystem and describe the attributes that enable the ecosystem to remain sustainably together.

2 Theoretical background

Mobility integrator services in platform-based business

The trends of efficient and green mobility (user focus and values, lifestyle responsive and seamless mobility) are shaping the landscape of transportation (Murray, 2013). Urban mobility involves multiple challenges as people increasingly gather to live in relatively small geographic areas. Today 64 % of the overall travel kilometers are urban and this number is estimated to triple by 2050 (Dixon, 2011). The challenge of managing this increasing growth and concentration of traffic along with its various environmental and social implications has been acknowledged in the European level (also in Horizon 2020) and the future scenario has been set to smart, green and integrated city transport.

The development of technologies and the increasing number of smart-device users has allowed the birth of *integrated mobility information services*. According to Motta et al. (2013, p. 97) a mobility integrator is: “an innovative approach that integrates Information & Planning, Transport Services, Infrastructure and Traffic Management. In short, it shall provide a smooth and convenient integrated mobility platform.” Following this type of business model means linking all transportation modes together to provide a variety of journey planning solutions (e.g. integrated information) and associated services for the passenger. Mobility integrators are seen as an important step towards accomplishing seamless multi-modal door-to-door travel. (Singh & Briggs, 2013)

Mobility integrators have been proven to create value for a variety of stakeholders. For example Motta et al. (2013) mention value elements such as environmental benefits (lowering energy and emissions through increased shared and public transportation), business benefits (optimization of transportation resources) and personal, mobile user benefits (easy travel definition and travel optimization). However, to be able to realize the benefits, collaborative efforts between a number of different players (such as transport operators, technology providers and authorities) are needed (Singh & Briggs, 2013).

To recap, business models for integrating transportation services and information into multimodal mobility networks creates significant value that is composed of multiple overlapping types of beneficial effects, i.e. value elements. At the offset, the collaboratively created value benefits the involved actors disproportionately to their required efforts and furthermore spills over to other stakeholders. This raises the critical requirement of reconciling the uneven distribution of benefits and efforts in creating, managing and sustaining the ecosystem.

Value creation and capture in platform-based ecosystems

Business ecosystems are economic communities, where a set of actors interact and coevolve together in a joint business playground (Moore, 1996). In these, the network of actors aim to create value for the customer by collaborative actions (Adner & Kapoor, 2010) delivering integrated solutions to end users (Clarysse et al. 2014). The power of this type of business has already been recognized in academic and business world (e.g. Iansiti & Levien, 2004; Cusumano, 2010) as many leading companies (such as Apple, and Airbnb) have overwhelmed incumbents by utilizing the power of ecosystems and more precisely platform-based business (Van Alstyne, et al., 2016). Platforms exist in continuous competition for members and customers on the basis of platform quality, indirect network effects, and consumer expectations (Zhu & Iansiti, 2012).

The aim of platform-based business ecosystems is to create value and exchanges between involved actors through common meeting space (Li, 2009). The value added is based on utilizing the interactions and information between two or more distinct user groups effectively creating two- or multi-sided markets (Evans, 2003; Evans & Schmalensee, 2007; Eisenmann et al., 2006), in which the number of participants in one side of the market determines the value creation possibilities in another (Van Alstyne et al., 2016). Platform strategies are dependent on this joint value creation benefiting all participant groups through fair and equitable value capture. Although value creation and capture are highly linked processes, they should be viewed separately as the creation of value does not bestow the ability to capture that value in the long run (Lepak et al., 2007). The focus on value capture (or value appropriation) sets directions for the management of business ecosystems (Ritala & Hurmelinna-Laukkanen, 2009).

Existing literature on ecosystems focuses on the importance of the hub firm in managing the value creation and extraction processes and its role in building and orchestrating the ecosystem (Ritala et al. 2013; Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006; Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011). Successful orchestration requires that hub firms carefully plan their actions taking into account factors addressing knowledge mobility, innovation and design and stability of the network. (Dhanaraj & Parkhe, 2006; Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011) Managing the business ecosystem requires understanding the (financial) value of the network and the positive value creation opportunities (i.e. benefits) for different stakeholders together with possible negative effects that may reduce the value experienced (Gawer & Cusumano, 2013). For example there may be negative feedback loops and network effects (Van Alstyne et al., 2016), tensions due to competing interests between stakeholders (Lepak et al. 2007) or trade-offs, as certain characteristics of the ecosystem may provide business benefits for one type of stakeholder, but increase the costs for another (Byggeth & Hohschorner, 2006; Hahn et al., 2010). Thus a deep understanding about the elements of the value for different stakeholder perspectives, i.e. platform owners, providers, producers, consumers and complementary parties, is critical for building a sustainable business model (Chesbrough, 2007) which allows sufficient value capture for all parties involved.

Business models for platform-based ecosystems

Finding the suitable business model for the commercialization and capturing economic value of an idea is not obvious (Chesbrough, 2013) and in ecosystems this is even more hampered by the number of involved stakeholders. Business model research has strongly focused on a single company perspective following general definition of: “the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010, p.). The research to open business models (Chesbrough, 2007; Sandulli & Chesbrough, 2009) extends the concept to the direction of networked and ecosystem-based business environments, mainly focusing on how business models may accommodate collaborative and open innovation approaches. Specifically, Sandulli & Chesbrough (2009) shortly discuss the opening of other resources as well, noting that “*normally, an open business model requires a tradeoff between breadth, depth and control over the shared resources.*” This has implications for the design of platform-based ecosystems, where governance and direction are accomplished by mutually accepted rules and policies instead of hierarchical control (Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011).

Platforms that are seeking to establish themselves are first faced with the ‘chicken-or-egg’ problem (Caillaud & Julien, 2003) inherent to multi-sided markets: unless there is a large enough user base, it is unlikely that service providers will join and vice versa. This is especially important for mobility information integrators where positive cross-side network effects (enabling access to services / customers) are potentially coupled with negative same-side effects (in-platform competition between service providers for the same customers). Architecture and governance choices in the design of the platform and business model are critical to overcoming the chicken-or-egg problem (Tiwana, 2014).

Once past the initial stage, the platform needs to cope with competition from rival platforms. When leveraging the ecosystem for innovation – that is critical for the sustained competitiveness of the platform (Gawer & Cusumano, 2013; Tiwana, 2014, p. XV) – the business model design needs to take into account for issues arising from diminished control of the innovation (Sandulli & Chesbrough, 2009). Ecosystem-based business models involve co-innovation risks (who else needs to innovate in order for your innovation to succeed?) and adoption chain risk (who else needs to adopt your innovation before end-consumer can assess it?) (Venkatraman & Lee, 2004).

More importantly, open business models and adopting an open innovation approach to developing the ecosystem and the underlying platform, can have profound effects on shifting the basis of competitive advantage (Reed & Storrud-Barnes, 2012) and even restructuring the industry (Weill & Woerner, 2015). Arora, Fosfuri and Gambardella (2001) argue that markets for knowledge (that grow from increasing open innovation) shift the basis of competition downstream closer to the customer, while eroding the importance of technology as the basis for competitive advantage. This implies that the competitive advantage of the owner of the platform is strengthened, as they control the distribution channel and access to information regarding market needs and demands (Weill & Woerner, 2015). Furthermore, other sources of competitive advantage such as reputation effects, customer switching costs and barriers to entry remain valid (Reed & Storrud-Barnes, 2012) and can be reinforced greatly by the platform. Correspondingly, firms relying on traditional, closed business models will find their competitiveness diminished (Weill & Woerner, 2015; Tiwana, 2014).

From ecosystem perspective this means that a hub firm needs to set attention on the diffusion of the network-based business model and create ways to manage value creation so that it can work as a base for the birth of sustainable ecosystem. In addition, if the business model is diffused successfully they need to consider on how to make it sustainable and continuous requiring sustainable value capture for all network partners.

3 Methodology

We combine the literature of ecosystems and multi-sided markets with the findings from the business model literature. Based on previous literature, we have compiled a list of competitive interests/compatibilities for value creation and capture working as a key for the sustaining development of an archetypal ecosystem-based business model. The list of these factors was further confirmed in focus group workshop in January 2016. After this, the factors were applied for the case platform.

As the research topic of value creation and capture in platform-based business is relatively new (Ritala et al. 2013), qualitative case study research approach was seen appropriate for the study. This enabled us to increase the understanding of the phenomenon

and capture a deep understanding of a complex issue in its natural setting. Furthermore, case study is especially applicable in addressing our “how” and “what” research questions and an exploratory approach supports theory building from empirical insights in an under-research area. (Eisenhardt & Gaebner, 2007; Yin, 2014)

We selected to use focus group methodology as a research technique for data collection as it offers valuable data by enabling in-depth discussion, and diversity among the participants (Liamputtong, 2011; Morgan, 1996; Morgan & Krueger, 1993). Focus group is a research technique where data is collected from group interaction (discussion) on a given topic, facilitated by researcher (Steward & Shamdasani, 2015). During focus groups participants query and explain themselves to other participants (Morgan, 1996). Focus groups can provide a great amount of valuable data, allow elaborating on motivations and understanding complex behaviors (Morgan & Krueger, 1993) thus being appropriate for this research. Furthermore, the method gives an ability to learn about participants’ perspectives by allowing meaningful discussions about the topics under research and is applicable for e.g. need assessment purposes (Morgan, 2008).

Case description

The studied case, DORA (Door to Door Information for Air Passengers and Airports), is an example of a “mobility integrator” (Singh & Briggs, 2013), where several organizations and players combine various products, services and information to offer final solution: a platform-based information system for traveling optimization. Actors are connected through a common mobile-based platform that brings together technological advances, information, data processing and other related services. The aim of DORA is to offer seamless and integrated information system that helps passengers to optimize their air and land traveling experience from the origin of the trip to the final destination. Moreover, the system is aiming to reduce the time needed for typical European air traveling. To ensure fluent traveling experience, DORA will integrate all necessary information (e.g. public transport and flight schedules, tickets, maps, airport routing and waiting times, disruptions in the land transport environments and on incidents in the airport terminals) to an open, mobile user-friendly environment.

The development of the system is in progress, which gave us an excellent chance to examine the conditions for business model creation. In DORA the value is created in multiple ways and divided across multiple stakeholders as are also the costs of maintaining the system. This requires the design of an appropriate business model, taking into account all the relevant issues in ensuring the value creation and capture for all parties within the network.

The figure 1 illustrates the value exchange and core stakeholders of DORA platform ecosystem. Firstly, the core framework involves the most crucial stakeholders (e.g. passenger, airports, airlines and transport operators) and features (e.g. development of software and secure information flows). The value is delivered for each stakeholder within DORA by managing information and money flows through the platform. For example, passenger can utilize combined travel information in optimizing the travel experience (time, money) and purchase tickets through DORA. Airport information allows passenger to move smoothly, whereas airport is provided information about passenger movements. This helps Airports to upgrade their security, optimizing personnel requirements and developing overall airport experience.

Secondly, after successful establishment of the core business solution, additional features and integration of new stakeholders (such as airport shops, cities, and information centers) may be implemented. The final part is to integrate DORA to other already established platforms (such as Tripadvisor). The sustainability of DORA operation may be solved by appropriate, dynamic networked business model(s) including the approach of open and continuous innovation. To foster the adoption of the system, DORA will be designed in a generic way providing open application for users.

Figure 1 The case platform ecosystem and value exchange

Focus group workshop

The international focus group workshop took place in Berlin, January 2016. To ensure diverse opinions, group included 22 participants representing high-level experienced people from organizations representing all key sides of the case platform: airports, airlines, service providers, passengers and city (see table 1).

Table 1 Expert workshop participants

<i>Participant group</i>	<i>Number of representat</i>	<i>Fields of expertise</i>
Airport	5	System engineering online technologies; Information and Communication Technology; National aerospace; Intermodality management; air consultancy; strategy, coordination, and sales management Strategy and integration management, Aeronautics research in Europe
Passenger	7	Technology and society; mobility and space research Management of life and health e-services; Transport and spatial planning; Telecommunications, group systems and real time distributed applications; Technology management and innovation software; Software engineering; Technology and science, project management, R&D of mobility & metropolitan global services
Service provider	5	Strategy & Business Development, online services; Public transportation; Software development; Traffic and mobility management; Passenger information management; public transportation; engineering
Airline	2	Business development & innovation management Innovation & strategic management
City/region	1	Project management; information and communications; R&D collaboration
Facilitator	2	Business and management; innovation management; industrial engineering

The workshop structure involved three parts: 1) Joint validation of the identified value elements (positive and negative) 2) Individual questionnaire regarding the assessment of the identified value elements 3) Discussion about creating sustainable platform-based business model for the case. The structure of the workshop and guiding questions are shown in table 2. The first part of the workshop was based on structured discussion led by facilitators. During the discussion, altogether 46 positive and 16 negative value elements regarding the participation to the platform were validated. This was followed by questionnaire that was personally filled by each participant (excluding facilitators). In this part, participants were asked to assess the validated value elements (positive value created/ value opportunities and negative value/value missed) for the case participation from the stakeholder perspective. This was done individually, each participant taking the perspective of stakeholder group they present. The assessment was done in 4 point scale with the answer options receiving a score between 0 and 4 as presented in table 3. Finally, the workshop concluded by a joint discussion about the creation of a sustainable business model around the case platform.

Table 2 Workshop structure

<i>Part</i>	<i>Content of the workshop</i>	<i>Guiding information and questions</i>
Part 1	Discussion: Verifying the list of identified value elements	<p><i>What value is created for different types of stakeholders?</i></p> <p><i>How is the value created?</i></p> <p><i>What is the value destroyed or missed? Are there negative outcomes for any of the stakeholders?</i></p> <p><i>How can negative outcomes be covered?</i></p>
Part 2	Assessment of the identified value elements a) Positive value created/value opportunities b) Negative value/value missed	<p><i>Assess the effect of the identified value element for the participation from the perspective of the stakeholder group you represent</i></p> <p><i>What value elements are relevant for stakeholder participation?</i></p>
Part 3	Discussion: creating sustainable platform-based business model for the case	<p><i>Who should cover the development and maintaining costs of the case?</i></p> <p><i>Besides offering the basic service for free for passengers, what can be done to attract a critical mass of passengers and service providers to the platform?</i></p> <p><i>How to induce lock-in?</i></p>

All discussions were facilitated by researcher and the primary researcher was accompanied by another researcher taking notes. Theoretical memos about initial interpretations were made after the debriefing of group discussions (Creswell, 2003). To ensure validity of the study (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), several actions were executed. For example, triangulation of data was used as field notes and questionnaires (and other data sources such as airport websites) were combined for analysis after the focus group. Providing the summary of the reports to participant validation and reviewing preliminary findings by multiple researchers involved were used to ensure the credibility and confirmability (Miles & Huberman, 1984). Furthermore, the overview of the findings was presented to academics and practitioners for review and feedback.

Table 3 Value element assessment scale

<i>Positive value created/value opportunities</i>					
<i>Value element</i>	No interest for participation	Participating without costs	Participating with costs	Active co-development	I cannot say/not relevant
Cost savings	1	2	3	4	0
<i>Negative value /value missed</i>					
	No significant effect	Tolerate without compensation	Tolerate with compensation	Active resist/leaving platform	I cannot say/not relevant
Increased costs	1	2	3	4	0

4 Findings

Duality and the relationships between value creation and value capture are the core issues in creating sustainable networked business models and need to be managed actively by the platform provider. Both value creation – and value capture aspects have their specific sets of requirements that guide the emergence of these issues. This is not only a case with one actor but when taking a network level perspective, the requirements of the entire ecosystem will be integrated. As the result of the focus group workshop 46 positive and 16 negative value elements regarding the participation to the platform were validated (see Annex, table 4).

The results of the value assessment indicate that the most important positive value elements for stakeholder participation have to do with maintaining fluent operations (e.g. prevention and mitigation of disruptive events, improved access to disruption information), improving services (e.g. improved service quality, increased intermodality and accessibility of airport) and saving costs. The most significant negative value elements on the other hand included negative economic effects (increases in costs), information security issues (information security and privacy) and business effects (e.g. negative image, increased work and competition). Although the early development was motivated by time and environmental saving effects, they were not eventually seen to be that relevant in ensuring platform lock-in.

To arrive at a shortlist of value elements we averaged the points assigned in the value assessment for each stakeholder group and included the value elements that scored in the top five by two or more stakeholder groups. The resulting shortlist of value elements prioritized by the network includes 15 positive and 9 negative value elements that are displayed in figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2 Top positive value elements groups for stakeholder participation

Figure 3 Top negative value elements for stakeholder participation

When analysing data by stakeholder groups, we focused on the shortlisted elements while also considering the others and identified some significant differences between the groups. For airports, the most important positive value element separating the group from others was *better optimization of capacity* allowing also *cost savings*. These are natural priorities for any airport development project, as cost efficiency and capacity improvements are key to the continuity and scalability of their everyday business. This together with the *improved accessibility of airport* and *improved customer information* were seen the most significant elements for active co-development of platform. On the other hand, *negative brand and image effects* which has much to do with *information security problems*, were aspects that needs to be avoided.

Airlines require clear economic business benefits (*cost savings, revenue, increased number of passengers and possibilities for personalization*) in order to participate actively to the development and maintaining the platform. Naturally *increases in costs, negative image and brand effects* as well as *distanced customer relationships* should be avoided as they are counteracting forces to the aforementioned benefits. Furthermore, they also highlighted the importance on solving the problem of *increasing emissions* which is key to reaching their sustainability targets.

Within service providers (transport operators), DORA may be seen as a threat first and the value creation possibilities may not be understood in the first place. Their business models face greater pressure to change when the industry reorganizes more towards a true ecosystem structure. For service providers the most important positive value elements were *increased customer information* and *lower information asymmetry* that also enable open business model innovation and potential associated first mover advantages. Informants highlighted the importance of *increased customer, traffic and disruption information* and *revenue*. The issues to be avoided included *increases in costs* and *negative image effects*. The focus group discussion noted the importance of the strong “green movement” in Europe adding to sustainability pressures for service providers. Addressing sustainability and social responsibility issues as value creators can in itself motivate service providers’ participation. DORA should offer two levels of participation: active users who both feed data in and receive data with neutral costs and a passive service option where the provider simply pays to use the service.

From individual passenger perspective, the active participation to maintaining and developing the platform was not seen as important. They aren’t typically willing to pay for the service but are interested to participate if the service could offer improved transportation services (*accessibility to the airport, improved travel network resiliency/robustness in case of disruptions*) and an easy way to maintain travelling (*increased supply for information connectivity and reliability*). *Extra work* and *increased costs* were seen as main problems emphasizing the importance of an easy-to-use and free of charge basic service. In terms of key value propositions this could translate to e.g. mobile one-stop ticketing directly from the app to all mobility services utilized on the trip. As awareness of sustainability is increasing passengers appreciate *lowering emissions* and thus *avoiding negative environmental effects*. Focus group discussants underlined the importance of promoting environmental and also social sustainability that resonate with the values of the end-users: “*Being developed as a European project combining public and private interests DORA is well situated to compete via promoting sustainability and may differentiate itself as a responsible, trustworthy and dependable platform that provides a service to the community.*”

For city/region perspective, there were no significant elements that should be highlighted. All the elements were seen to be important and improving the region while the general attitude towards actively contributing to the development of the ecosystem was positive. From the possible value reducing elements, the *information security* issues were seen the most important thing to be handle with care. Realizing a mobility integrator platform by necessity entails connecting various information sources and platforms while maintaining data security in a complex cloud service that in itself constitutes a considerable technical challenge and social risk (Motta et al., 2013). However, public stakeholders stand to gain from the platform by it optimizing the use of multimodal mobility systems and infrastructure, adding to their resilience to disruptions as well as improving public service provision with co-organized services such as healthcare. Participating in DORA may thus constitute a cost-effective way of coping with the capacity and service level demands to the transport system, avoiding undue congestion and providing e.g. a tool for crisis management situations or means to arrange optimized airport access to health services.

In summary, a sustainable business model for DORA depends on covering the costs of operation and development in a fair and agreeable way. There is a possibility to distribute costs among private stakeholders (service providers, airports, airlines) but also with public stakeholders (cities or regions). The overall value created by orchestrating mobility services in an ecosystem enabled by the DORA platform is largely due to improving access to information and options as well as reducing overall time spent travelling, but from the perspective of the involved stakeholders the apparent value is in scaling their operations cost-effectively by constituting an efficient distribution channel for mobility services. This effectively brings us back to the core issue of any platform-based business model, that is, the chicken-and-egg problem (Caillaud & Julien, 2003) of attracting a critical mass of users on all sides of the multi-sided market in question.

DORA will compete for the attention of end-users and other stakeholders in a market already populated by dozens of solutions with generally more focused services or only partial coverage of the door-to-door journey, none of which currently are able to offer the full extent of services as DORA (Willing et al., 2016). More specialized (privately operated) services are likely able to benefit from faster development cycles and privileged access to the individual service providers' data and offerings (such as in the case of an airport that provides their own app). The competitive advantage of DORA as a complete mobility integrator is in the added value enabled by integrating the full range of services and information across the whole travel chain. This unique position allows value propositions based on a seamless experience and complete mobility information access from one interface point. This also allows more effective optimization and routing that is able to adapt to individual preferences and dynamic changes in the travel chain, such as real-time reactivity to disruptions. Furthermore, DORA is able to connect multiple sources to provide transparent and reliable information based on real-time monitoring and maintain a neutral stance (not being privately owned and operated by one service provider) to guarantee fair and equal treatment of all stakeholders.

According to focus group discussion, to attract a critical mass of passengers and service providers to the platform and commit them to it requires consideration of B2B information but also taking a B2C approach. Generating sufficient switching costs to induce end user lock-in can be achieved by simplifying their travel planning and minimizing the effort of the user while retaining their access to all travel options. This requires compounding of multiple functions into one, fluent application. Trust towards the platform should be created and maintained by providing correct, reliable and accurate information at all times.

Technically this may require for instance enhancing the time estimates provided by transport operators by real-time monitoring and disruption information. Then again to compel service providers to join and contribute to the platform it needs to remain neutral, provide cost-effective access to the customers and improve their services through integration with the platform. Mobility information service and application development, while quickly becoming a necessity for many transport operators, is not their core business and as such they often lack capabilities and resources to manage it effectively. Therefore, DORA may act as an important complement to their business by providing them with the service and effectively allowing them to avoid investing in developing the capability themselves. As one of the informants mentioned “*to get a wide scale of service providers involved quickly, you have to have a situation where you can say ‘We have developed an app for you and no significant investments are needed’.*”

5 Discussion and implications

The focus of the study was on examining case DORA - a platform-based information system for traveling optimization. The widespread adoption of an extensive mobility integrator platform such as DORA transforms the competitive environment by drastically reducing the asymmetries of information and in doing so reducing market imperfections and inefficiencies. While this is a positive net gain on the overall level, and specifically for end users and society, at the same time it may weaken the business models of transport operators that have capitalized on those imperfections. This creates mixed incentives for the service providers when making the decision to join the platform: on one hand the platform offers an efficient distribution channel to its user base, while on the other hand it may require investment and business model innovation to profit from it.

Reorganizing economic activity to an ecosystem configuration requires the involved stakeholders to consider multiple parallel changes to their business. The conceptualization of value moves to the network level where complex interactions take place and result in value emerging from co-opetitive relationships, co-created with customers (Hearn & Pace, 2006) and redistributed within the network via an orchestrated activity (Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011) supported by a software platform which evolves through open innovation directed both at the platform and within the complementary services provided through it (Gawer & Cusumano, 2011). Firm strategies and business models need to adapt to account for their relation to value ecologies (Hearn & Pace, 2006) and determine suitable levels of involvement that account both for the private interest of the participating firm as well as the long term health of the network with which its future prospects are entwined (Iansiti & Levien, 2004). The participants together create value for the platform, but are also expecting to receive their share of the total value generated. Managing the expectations of the prospective participants is essential in order for the platform to be attractive (Adner, 2006) and there needs to be a network-level business model in place that is seen to be fair and equitable in sharing costs and revenues created collaboratively (Nambisan & Sawhney, 2011). As the research of conditions for value capture (or appropriation) is relatively new in studying software platforms (Ceccagnoli et al., 2012) our study opens interesting areas for future discussion.

The DORA platform covers the entire travel chain from door to door for the air passenger providing her with information and services covering all the possible mobility options and essential related choices. This requires an ecosystem of actors spanning both

public and private stakeholders all of which need to be able to collaborate to create value and share efforts in developing and maintaining the platform while innovating on the services provided. Therefore, the business model should account for the complexity by allowing multiple levels of involvement ranging from passive participation with compensation (for e.g. transport operators) or without (passengers using the core service) to active co-development (for e.g. cities, transport information centers or airports). Each stakeholder group has a set of interests that partially overlap but may also conflict causing tensions that need to be carefully communicated and managed by the design and governance of the platform in order to reach an equilibrium state where all parties are incentivized to sustain their commitment to the platform. Certain stakeholder groups have clear individual requirements that need to be satisfied to commit them to DORA. Passengers should have a minimal threshold for engaging with the platform, thus requiring free or negligible cost of use, a seamless and fluent user experience that minimizes efforts. Service providers seek to gain cost-efficient access to a powerful distribution channel that allows them to avoid investment in building proprietary online services to scale their business. Airports and cities alike seek to maximize their capacity and provide an improved level of service. In addition to these stakeholder-specific requirements, all parties share interests pertaining to the platform and its governance that must be satisfied. These include technical and social concerns of information and data security, economic and moral concerns of fair treatment, equal representation and sharing of costs, risks and efforts as well as societal values, especially improving the sustainability of the transport system.

The limitations of the study are related to its qualitative nature. The focus of our study was on examining the creation and sustaining platform-based business model in mobility integrator context. Although the limited setting of the study, we believe that the results provide interesting implications to managers working or willing to work in ecosystem based business. The focus of the study was especially in increasing the understanding of ecosystem based business model development by taking into account innovation inputs and incentives, simultaneous examination of attracting and keeping members and discuss how the hub firm may lead the ecosystem by managing this business model. The study offers managerial guidance in business model development especially for platform operators in business areas connecting public and private partners (such as mobility). Future research should be continued to various types of industries and settings. In addition, the utilization of qualitative methods could offer significant inputs for example in investigating the relationships and cross-effects of value creation and capture between different stakeholder groups. Furthermore, it could be interesting to expand the research from studying core participant groups to additional stakeholders such as wider scale of service providers and other platforms. This interesting avenue for the future research could provide new opportunities for innovation within the ecosystem

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Annex

Table 4 Value elements

<i>Level of value analysis</i>	<i>Positive value created /value opportunities</i>	<i>Negative value/ value missed</i>
Individual	<i>Effects on time</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less time at airports, more free-time, More leisure time at airports, Travel time reduction, Time savings, Reduced travel planning time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less time at airports Travel time reduction
	<i>Effects on experiment</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased satisfaction with routing, Increased possibilities for personalization, More options, Increased attractiveness of air-transport, Inclusive transport services for users with special needs, Lower threshold of seeking options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy, Distanced customer relationships
Organization level	<i>Financial effects</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost savings, Revenue, Lower cost of travel, Lower marketing costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased costs
	<i>Business opportunities</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New business opportunities, New technological solutions, Rise of mobility management providers, Complements other web services, Increased image/ reputation effects, Improved service quality, Added use of transport services, Increased number of passengers/ customers, Increased customer information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased competition, Brand dilution, Negative image effects, Less work, Rise of mobility management providers, platform lock-in
	<i>Resource efficiency</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better optimization of capacity, Increased energy efficiency, Increased resource efficiency, Less work, Less stress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased work
Social level	<i>Information management effects</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy access to information (e.g. price, emissions), Increased supply for information connectivity and reliability, Lower information asymmetry, Improved access to disruption information, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information security, Increased information, Information transparency
	<i>Disruption management effects</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention and mitigation of disruptive events, Travel network resiliency/ robustness in case of disruptions 	
	<i>Transportation effects</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased efficiency and attractiveness of public transport, increased intermodality and travelling/ mobility, <i>Better connected air transport and accessibility of airport</i>, Better connected cities 	
	<i>Environmental effects</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less private cars, Lower emissions, Shift to greener mobility and promotion of sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased emissions